

CREATION OF MODELS OF PHYSICAL PHENOMENA AND PHYSICAL BODIES USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.

I.A. Atashov

3rd year undergraduate student in physics at Karakalpak State University. Berdak. Nukus

A.S. Kalilaev

teacher at the Department of Physics, Karakalpak State University. Berdak, Nukus.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179713>

Abstract. *This answer discusses examples of the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in physics. AI can be used to model the properties of materials, analyze experimental data, model complex systems, optimize experiments, and search for new physical laws. The use of AI in physics opens up new opportunities for more accurate modeling and understanding of physical phenomena.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, physics, modeling, data analysis, optimization, experiments, materials, complex systems, physical laws.*

СОЗДАНИЕ МОДЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ ЯВЛЕНИЙ И ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ ТЕЛ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА.

Аннотация. *В данном ответе обсуждаются примеры применения искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в физике. ИИ может использоваться для моделирования свойств материалов, анализа экспериментальных данных, моделирования сложных систем, оптимизации экспериментов и поиска новых физических законов. Применение ИИ в физике открывает новые возможности для более точного моделирования и понимания физических явлений.*

Ключевые слова: *Искусственный интеллект, физика, моделирование, анализ данных, оптимизация, эксперименты, материалы, сложные системы, физические законы.*

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) has led to the possibility of creating models of physical phenomena and physical bodies using new approaches and methods. AI is a powerful tool capable of processing and analyzing huge amounts of data, as well as finding complex patterns and relationships between physical phenomena. This makes it a valuable tool for creating models that can help in understanding and predicting various physical processes.

In this work, we will consider the main approaches and examples of using artificial intelligence in physics to create models of physical phenomena and physical bodies. We will

explore various techniques such as machine learning, neural networks, genetic algorithms and expert systems that can be applied to model and analyze physical systems.

Creating accurate and efficient models of physical phenomena is an important task because they can be used to predict system behavior, optimize processes, and develop new technologies.

The application of artificial intelligence in physics opens up new horizons and helps improve our understanding of the fundamental laws of nature.

Next, we will consider the main aspects of creating models of physical phenomena and physical bodies using artificial intelligence, and also consider examples of their application in various fields of physics.

The basics of artificial intelligence (AI) in physics include various methods and approaches that allow you to create models of physical phenomena and physical bodies. Some of the main aspects of artificial intelligence used in physics are:

1. Machine learning and neural networks:

- Machine learning is a technique that allows a computer to learn from data and experience, without explicit programming. This allows AI models to adapt to new information and improve their performance.

- Neural networks are models that imitate the functioning of the human nervous system. They consist of many connected artificial neurons and are used for data analysis, pattern recognition, forecasting and other tasks.

2. Genetic algorithms and evolutionary modeling:

- Genetic algorithms are optimization techniques inspired by the principles of natural selection and genetics. They are used to find optimal solutions by emulating the process of evolution and selecting the most suitable options.

- Evolutionary modeling is an approach that creates models that emulate evolutionary processes such as mutation and selection to study and optimize physical systems.

3. Expert systems and knowledge bases:

- Expert systems are programs that use the knowledge of experts in a particular field to make decisions and solve complex problems. In physics, they can be used to model and predict physical phenomena based on accumulated experience and knowledge.

- Knowledge bases are repositories of information containing facts, rules and laws necessary to create models of physical phenomena. They can be used in combination with AI techniques to analyze and infer new knowledge.

Artificial intelligence in physics provides the opportunity to create more accurate and efficient models of physical phenomena and physical bodies. It allows you to analyze complex

data, find hidden patterns, predict the behavior of systems and optimize physical processes. This opens up new opportunities for scientific research, developing new technologies and improving our understanding of the fundamental laws of nature.

Creating models of physical phenomena is an important aspect of research in physics.

Models of physical phenomena are abstract representations of real physical systems that allow us to describe and explain their behavior.

There are several approaches to creating models of physical phenomena:

1. Analytical models:

- Analytical models are based on mathematical equations that describe physical laws and interactions between system components. These models are usually used in cases where the physical laws are well known and accurate analytical solutions can be obtained.

- An example of an analytical model can be a model of body motion under the influence of gravitational force, described by Newton's equations.

2. Numerical models:

- Numerical models are based on dividing a physical system into many small elements or particles, and numerically solving equations for each element. These models allow for more complex interactions and nonlinearities to be taken into account.

- Numerical modeling methods include finite element method, finite difference method and particle method.

3. Statistical models:

- Statistical models rely on the analysis of statistical data and probability distributions to describe the behavior of a system. They are often used to model random processes and stochastic systems.

- An example of a statistical model would be a model of the energy distribution in a system of many particles at a given temperature.

4. Models based on artificial intelligence:

- Artificial intelligence can be used to create models of physical phenomena using machine learning techniques, neural networks and genetic algorithms. These models can process large amounts of data and find complex patterns in systems.

When creating models of physical phenomena, it is important to consider the constraints and assumptions that go into the model. In addition, models must be validated and compared with experimental data to ensure their accuracy and applicability. Building models of physical phenomena is an iterative process that requires interaction between theory, experiment, and computational methods to achieve accurate and predictable results.

Creating models of physical bodies is an important aspect in physics and engineering. Models of physical bodies are used to describe and predict their behavior, characteristics, and interactions with other bodies or the environment. Here are some basic approaches to creating models of physical bodies:

1. Analytical models:

- Analytical models of physical bodies are based on mathematical equations that describe their geometry, structure, and the physical laws to which they obey. These models provide analytical solutions for body characteristics and behavior.

- An example of an analytical model would be the model of spring motion described by Hooke's law.

2. Numerical models:

- Numerical models of physical bodies are used to solve complex equations that describe their behavior using numerical methods. These models break down a physical body into many small elements and numerically solve equations for each element.

- Finite element method (Finite Element Method) is one of the most common numerical methods for modeling physical bodies. It breaks down a body into finite elements and solves equations for each element, taking into account their geometry, material properties and external forces.

3. Physical simulations:

- Physical simulations use computer models and algorithms to simulate the physical behavior of the body. They take into account physical laws, such as the laws of conservation of energy and angular momentum, and model the interaction of a body with its environment.

- An example of a physical simulation could be modeling the motion of a rigid body in a gravitational field or modeling the deformation of a material under the influence of a force.

4. Models based on artificial intelligence:

- Artificial intelligence can be used to create models of physical bodies using machine learning techniques and neural networks. These models can process body behavior data and find hidden patterns, allowing them to predict their behavior under different conditions.

When creating models of physical bodies, it is important to take into account the characteristics of a particular system, material properties, environment and other factors that may influence their behavior. In addition, models must be validated and compared with experimental data to confirm their accuracy and applicability. Creating models of physical bodies requires a combination of theoretical knowledge, experimental data and computational methods to achieve accurate and predictable results.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly important role in physics, providing new capabilities for modeling, data analysis and solving complex physics problems. Here are some examples of the use of artificial intelligence in physics:

1. Predicting Material Properties: AI can be used to predict the properties of materials based on their structure and composition. Neural networks and genetic algorithms can be used to model and optimize materials with specified characteristics, such as strength, conductivity, and thermal conductivity.

2. Experimental Data Analysis: AI can be used to analyze complex data obtained from experiments. Machine learning and image processing techniques can be applied to automatically recognize and classify physical phenomena based on experimental data, helping researchers gain a more complete understanding of physical processes.

3. Modeling complex systems: AI can be used to model and simulate complex physical systems such as the Earth's atmosphere, galaxies, or the brain. Neural networks and genetic algorithms allow the creation of models that take into account many variables and nonlinear interactions, which helps researchers better understand and predict the behavior of such systems.

4. Experiment optimization: AI can be used to optimize experimental parameters to achieve the best results. Machine learning algorithms and optimization techniques can help researchers choose the most effective ways to set up experimental conditions and analyze large amounts of data collected during experiments.

5. Finding new laws of physics: AI can be used to explore large amounts of data and find hidden patterns, which can lead to the discovery of new physical laws and principles. Deep learning and automated knowledge extraction algorithms can help researchers identify new trends and connections in data that can lead to new discoveries and understanding of fundamental physical processes.

These are just a few examples of the use of artificial intelligence in physics. Advances in AI continue to open up new possibilities for research and solving complex physics problems, improving our understanding of the world and facilitating progress in science and technology.

In conclusion, the application of artificial intelligence in physics provides unique opportunities for deeper understanding of physical phenomena and solving complex problems.

Modeling, data analysis, optimization of experiments and the search for new laws become more efficient and accurate through the use of artificial intelligence methods. This allows researchers and engineers to make more informed decisions, create new materials with desired properties, and predict the behavior of complex systems. The application of artificial intelligence

in physics continues to evolve and is expected to lead to new discoveries and innovations in science and technology.

REFERENCES

1. I. A. Atashov , J. R. Xojamuratova « MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH » VOLUME 3 / ISSUE 4 / UIF :8.2 / MODERNSCIENCE . Uz . FIZIKADAN M Á SELELER T Ú RLER Í H Á M OLARDI SHESH Í W USILLARI . <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11004477>
2. Kalilaev, A. S., & Atashov, I. A. (2024). USE OF MICROSOFT EXCEL IN PHYSICS LABORATORY EXERCISES. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 27–32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10812576>
3. A. S. Kalilaev, IAAatashov . International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers. ISSN: 2945-4492 (online) | (SJIF) = 8.09 Impact factor. 2024 Published: |22-04-2024| “BA-137 M IZOTOPINING YARIM YEMIRILISH DAVRINI ANIQLASH” LABORATORIYA ISHIDA RADIOAKTIV YEMIRILISHGA OID PARAMETLARNI O'RGANISH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990086>
4. Atashov IA, AAAbdreymov "MODERN SCIENCE AND ND RESEARCH" VOLUME 3 / ISSUE 4 / UIF:8.2 / MODERNSCIENCE.UZ FIZIK FORMULA QANDAY ISHLAB CHIQLADI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11044804>
5. "Machine Learning for Physics Discovery" - article from Google Research, available on arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.10563>
6. "Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Materials Science" - review article published in the journal Advanced Theory and Simulations: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adts.202000064>
7. " Deep Learning in Experimental Physics" - article published in the journal Reviews of Modern Physics: <https://journals.aps.org/rmp/abstract/10.1103/RevModPhys.91.045003>
8. "Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Physical Sciences" - article from ScienceDirect , available By address :<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S266638642030008X>
9. "Artificial intelligence in materials science: recent advances and prospects" - overview article published in Materials Today : <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1369702118305214>